

INCLUSIVE SPECIAL EDUCATION: A POLITICAL AND EDUCATIONAL VISION

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ABSTRACT

This work aimed to promote reflection on the inclusion of people with needs in regular schools. Based on bibliographical research, it was studied, described and began to better understand the inclusion of these people and how this inclusion would best be achieved through new proposals to meet their needs and the needs of the professionals who will work with them. Achieving inclusion takes work, it means “restructuring schools to accommodate the entire spectrum of human diversity represented by potential students, that is, people with physical disabilities...” (SASSAKI, 1998). Restructuring would not be limited to an isolated course or seminar, but rather a true transformation of schools and continuous training and monitoring, so that they can truly transform their educational practice. Hence the need to encourage students with special educational needs to develop their skills, creativity and socialization. Inclusion is a process for which there are no ready-made formulas, it requires everyone to be constantly improving and building. A permanent search for guidance and support from assistance associations and medical and educational authorities.

Keywords: Inclusion; Diversity; restructuring.

INTRODUCTION

Brazilian educational policy focused on special education reached the 1970s as one of the priorities of educational policy, embodied by the creation of the National Center for Special Education (CENESP), with the purpose of promoting, throughout the national territory, the expansion and the improvement of care for exceptional people, covering pre-school, 1st and 2nd degree levels, higher education and supplementary education, involving those with visual, hearing, mental and physical disabilities, students with conduct problems, those with multiple disabilities and the gifted (Articles 1 and 2 of Decree no. 72,425, of 07/03/73).

The government of the state of São Paulo, anticipating the federal government, had already created its Special Education service, together with the Department of Education, through Decree no. 47,186, dated 11/21/66, continuing the care of exceptional cases through the combination of the various existing services.

Thus, São Paulo was one of the states of the federation that made the most progress in relation to exceptional care, which means that the analysis of its performance can offer significant data to deepen the understanding of educational policies related to special education, as the The São Paulo government assumed, alongside the private sector, practically all responsibility for the care of exceptional children, in terms of offering places in public schools located in the state.

Created in 1973, the National Center for Special Education (CENESP) took the initial step of establishing guidelines for its action. Assuming that Brazil, faithful to its democratic traditions, has made efforts to educate some types of exceptional people, such as those with visual impairments, hearing impairments and mental disabilities, lacking, however, the definition of an action policy that extends to all exceptional areas, took effective action in relation to special education, incorporating it as one of the education priorities, including it in the Education and Culture Sector Plan – 1972/1974.

Thus, the inclusion of special education as a priority in the Sector Plan and the creation of the body itself represented the implementation of the philosophy and policy expressed in that document and with the responsibility of promoting, throughout the National Territory, the expansion and improvement of care for exceptional people. , assisting public and private entities in rationalizing efforts, encouraging them in their initiatives and providing them with all technical and financial assistance, when necessary.

When defining its action based on these findings, CENESP presented the situation of special education in Brazil as if it already covered the entire population with hearing, visual and

mental disabilities, and should, in this sense, expand to other areas of exceptionality, which did not correspond to reality, since in 1974 this same body carried out a statistical survey on the care of exceptional people in Brazil. The fact that the foundations for CENESP's action include financial cooperation for private initiatives makes clear the position of transferring public funds to finance the private special education network, a phenomenon similar to what occurred in the regular education network.

Based on the identification of a series of difficulties and distortions existing in Brazilian special education (lack of connection between the federal, state, municipal areas and the private sector; dispersion of efforts between the areas of education, health, work, justice and social assistance ; lack of criteria for allocating funds and evaluating their employment; precarious data on the number of exceptional people cared for and the quality of care offered; precariousness of the services provided by the federated units), CENESP established two basic guidelines for action: integration and rationalization.

The first of the guidelines was characterized by the integration of the exceptional in relation to themselves and society, the areas of care (education, health, work, justice, social assistance) and the orbits in which their care was processed (federal, state, municipal , private initiative, community in general). The second was characterized by systemic planning based on surveys and diagnoses, by action that was based on the equation of objective-resources-limitations variables, by the full use of human and material resources, by the exchange of experiences and by the continuous monitoring and evaluation of activities developed.

Two major lines of action resulted from these two guidelines: the expansion of opportunities for educational assistance to exceptional people and technical support for special education to be provided.

In relation to the first, based on the need to expand educational opportunities for exceptional people, the body defined that this expansion should be guided by safe diagnosis and continuous assessment to provide referral:

- For specialized institutions, exceptional patients who can only be cared for in that type of institution;
- For regular schools, all exceptional students who can attend them , providing them with special assistance.

In addition to the inclusion of the disabled, which had been the focus of concern for State action since imperial times, this document includes, for the first time, the gifted in the list

of public power actions. Regarding the second, he defined the following as essential for the qualification of special education:

- Human resources adequately prepared for the service;
- Surveys, studies, research and experimentation;
- Joint programming of the areas of education with those of health, work, justice and social assistance.

These three priorities, according to the same document, should be considered by 1977, when, with sufficient human resources, data on reality and the results of studies and research, the priority would be to expand enrollment in special education.

The first consideration to be made regarding the guidelines and lines of action concerns the panorama of Brazilian special education outlined by the federal body to determine these guidelines. The lack of integration, the dispersion of efforts, the lack of criteria for allocating funds, precarious data, etc., constitute the visible aspect of the problem of the education of exceptional people. Not that they are not important, but, as the analysis of exceptionality was confined within such narrow limits, other determinants that prevent access to education for exceptional children were covered up.

When treating exceptionality as an ahistorical concept, the vision of a harmonious society was reiterated, in which the difficulties of integration reside in the “particular characteristics of each type of exceptionality”, and furthermore, class distinction is excluded. which, in our society, means that exceptional people from the lower classes are doubly penalized.

This narrow vision resulted in two basic guidelines for action: integration and rationalization, which privileged administrative actions as the safe way to consider and resolve the access of exceptional people to schooling, and resulted in technical procedures, that is, in safe diagnoses that would determine referrals appropriate.

THE INCLUSIVE SCHOOL

Sasaki (1997) states that Inclusive Education is understood as the process of including people with special needs or learning disorders in the common education network in all its levels, from pre-school to higher education. Through it, school projects are prioritized, which have the following characteristics:

1. A focus on the Community: In inclusive schools, the educational process is understood as a social process, where all children with special needs and learning disorders have the right to schooling as close to normal as possible. The target to be achieved is the integration of children with disabilities into the community.

2. Vanguard: An inclusive school is a leading school in relation to others. It presents itself as the vanguard of the educational process. Its main objective is to make the school act at all levels to enable the integration of the children who are part of it.

3. High Standards: in relation to inclusive schools, there are high performance expectations from all children involved. The goal is to help children reach their full potential. The process must be tailored to the needs of each child.

4. Collaboration and cooperation: there is a focus on social relationships between all school participants, with a view to creating a self-help network.

5. Changing roles and responsibilities: The inclusive school changes the traditional roles of teachers and school technical staff. Teachers become closer to students, in understanding their greatest difficulties. Support for regular class teachers is essential for the smooth running of the teaching-learning process.

6. Establishment of a service infrastructure: the inclusive school will gradually create a support network to overcome its greatest difficulties. An inclusive school is a school integrated into its community.

7. Partnership with parents: parents are essential partners in the process of including a child in school.

8. Flexible educational environments: educational environments must focus on the student's teaching-learning process.

9. Research-based strategies: changes to the school should be introduced based on discussions with the technical team, students, parents and teachers.

10. Establishment of new forms of assessment: old assessment criteria should be changed to meet the needs of students with disabilities.

11. Access: physical access to the school must be facilitated for individuals with disabilities.

12. Continuity in the professional development of the technical team: participants in the inclusive school must seek to continue their studies, deepening them.

ADVANCES IN SCHOOL INCLUSION

Araújo (1999) argues that the topic of Inclusion of disabled children has never been so present in day-to-day education. But this was not always the case, quite the opposite. In the past, disabled people were segregated, removed from any social interaction, as their difference was seen as a curse, destiny and all types of beliefs. After all, what was different was unknown and mysterious, and the unknown was a source of fear. From fear to prejudice, it was one step.

From the 19th century onwards, a time of great discoveries in the fields of medicine, biology and health, people with disabilities began to be studied in order to look for answers to your problems. Thus began what is called institutional segregation. The disabled were treated as sick in some institutions. Excluded from family and society, people with disabilities were welcomed into religious or philanthropic asylums, often spending their entire lives there. At the same time, some special schools and rehabilitation centers emerged, as society began to admit that disabled people could be productive if they received adequate training.

Bueno (1999) explains that, in Brazil, special assistance for people with disabilities officially began on October 12, 1854, when D. Pedro II. founded the *Imperial Instituto dos Meninos Cegos*, in Rio de Janeiro. In 1942, when there were already 40 (forty) regular public schools in the country that provided some assistance to mentally disabled people and 14 (fourteen) that served students with other disabilities, the Benjamin Constant Institute published in Braille the *Revista Brasileira para Cegos*, the first of its kind in Brazil.

Little by little, thanks to NGOs, such as the Pestalozzi Society, the AACD (Association for the Support of Disabled Children), the APAE, (Association of Parents and Friends of the Exceptional), the issue of disability was leaving the scope of health to the scope of education; creating the perception that disabled people are not sick.

The issue of including children with special needs in the regular education network falls within the context of discussions, increasingly in evidence, regarding the integration of people with disabilities as citizens, with their respective rights and duties of participation and contribution Social. Thus, the need for a special education policy emerged in the 1970s, when the MEC assumed that the Special Education clientele was those who required special care at home, at school and in society.

Da Ross (1999) clarifies that, in 1986, *axceptional* terms, it was replaced by *students with special needs*. In 1990, Brazil finally participated in the World Conference on Education for All, in the city of Jontei, Thailand. The seeds of Inclusive Education were sown.

In 1993, the United Nations standards on equal opportunities for people with disabilities were launched, which call on states to ensure that the education of people with disabilities is an integral part of the education system.

At the 1994, aWorld Conference on Special Educational Needs, in Salamanca, Spain, it recognizes and reaffirms the commitment to guaranteeing education for children, young people and adults with special educational needs within the framework of the regular education system; the *Salamanca Declaration* comes into force .

THE MEANING AND IMPORTANCE OF INCLUSIVE EDUCATION

According to Miller (2002, p. 28), inclusion “is the ability to understand and recognize others and, thus, have the privilege of living and sharing with people different from us. Inclusive education welcomes all people without exception". It applies to students with physical disabilities, those with mental impairments, gifted students, all minorities and children who are discriminated against for any other reason.

Da Ross (2002) states that the school has to be a reflection of life on the outside. The big gain, for everyone, is to live the experience of difference. If students do not go through this in childhood, later on they will have great difficulty overcoming prejudices. Inclusion enables those who are discriminated against due to disability, social class or color to, by right, occupy their space in society. If this does not happen, these people will always be dependent and have a half-baked life as a citizen. No one can have a place in the world without considering that of others, valuing what they are and what they can be. Furthermore, the greatest gain for a society is in guaranteeing everyone the right to education.

According to Carvalho (1997), what makes a school inclusive is, firstly, a good pedagogical project, which begins with reflection. Contrary to what many may think, inclusion is more than having ramps and adapted bathrooms. The inclusive school team must discuss why there is so much repetition and indiscipline, why teachers are not doing the job and why parents are not participating. A good project values the culture, history and previous experiences of the class.

Pedagogical practices also need to be reviewed. How are activities selected and planned so that everyone learns? Currently, many schools diversify the program, but hope that in the end everyone will have the same results. Students need the freedom to learn in their own way, according to their conditions. And this applies to students with disabilities or not.

Mantoan (1997) asks and answers a very important question: “How is inclusion in Brazil today?” And he states that Brazil is moving slowly in this regard. The biggest problem is that education networks and schools do not comply with the law. Our Constitution has guaranteed, since 1988, access for everyone to Elementary Education, and students with special needs must receive specialized assistance - preferably at school -, which does not replace regular education. There is another issue, a resistance movement that tries to prevent the inclusion of walking: the corporate strength of specialized institutions, mainly in mental disabilities. Many people continue to believe that the best thing is to exclude and keep children in special schools, which provide adapted education. But there has already been progress. Today, most people know that they have the right to go to regular school. We are in a very broad awareness process.

Mantoan (1997) also states that the school needs to adapt for inclusion. In addition to making physical adaptations, the school needs to offer specialized educational services alongside regular classes, preferably in the same location. Thus, a blind child, for example, attends classes with sighted classmates and, after shifts, trains mobility, locomotion, use of Braille language and instruments such as the soroban, to do math. All of this helps with your integration inside and outside of school.

Another important problem to be faced is how to guarantee specialized care if the school does not offer the conditions. Ferreira (1998) explains that public schools that do not receive pedagogical support or funding have the option of forming partnerships with special education entities, available in most networks. Meanwhile, the management must continue to demand from directors the support provided for by *em lei*. In the private school system. The specialized service can also come through partnerships - and must be offered at no cost to parents.

According to Carvalho (1997), students with severe mental disabilities can study in a regular class. Inclusion does not admit any type of discrimination, and those most excluded are always those with serious disabilities. In Canada, the aforementioned theorist claims to have seen a boy who went to school on a stretcher and, despite his compromised reasoning, was respected by his classmates, integrated into the class and participative. There are cases, however, in which the child is unable to interact because they are having an outbreak and need to be treated. So that the teacher knows the appropriate time to refer you to treatment, it is important to maintain links with clinical and specialized care.

The assessment of students with mental disabilities should not be differentiated. Ferreira (1998) states that a good assessment is one planned for everyone, in which the student learns to analyze their production critically and autonomously. He must say what he learned, what he finds interesting to study and how the knowledge acquired changes his life. Assessing

emancipated students is, for example, asking them to invent a test themselves. This way, they show how much they assimilated content. Applying tests with consultation is also much more productive than charging for memorization. The function of assessment is not to measure whether the child has reached a certain point; but if she grew up. This merit comes from personal effort to overcome your limitations, and not from comparison with others.

Ferreira (1998) states that an untrained teacher can teach students with disabilities. The role of the teacher is to be the class leader, not a specialist, em deficiência. Essa the responsibility lies with the specialized service team. There can be no confusion. A deaf child, for example, learns Libras (Brazilian sign language) and lip reading with the specialist. To become literate in the Portuguese language for the deaf, known as L2, the child is assisted by a Portuguese language teacher who is qualified to do so.

The conductor's role is to work on the content; However, partnerships between professionals are very productive. If there is a deaf child in the class and the teacher is going to teach a lesson about Egypt, the specialist shows the child photos, pictures and videos on the subject in advance. The L2 teacher gives the meaning of new words, such as pyramid and pharaoh. During class, visual support material, texts and lip reading facilitate understanding of the content.

According to Ferreira (1998) it is possible to teach blind and deaf people without mastering Braille and sign language. Canzian (1997) says that it is even positive if a deaf child's teacher does not know Libras, because he or she has to understand written Portuguese. Having knowledge of pounds makes communication easier; but, it is not essential for the class. If there is a blind person in the class, the teacher does not need to master Braille, because the student is the one who writes. He can even learn it if he thinks he needs it to correct texts; However, there is the option of asking a specialist for help. It is just not considered necessary to teach Libras and Braille in initial teacher training.

The teacher cannot refuse to teach inclusive classes, even if the school does not offer structure. Education networks are not giving schools and teachers what they need to do good work. Many avoid complaining for fear of losing their job or suffering persecution. But, they have to resort to the help that is available, the union, for example, where they legally expose how they are being harmed professionally. Parents and community leaders can also promote dialogue with networks, putting pressure on them to comply with the law.

The Public Prosecutor's Office monitors, generally based on complaints, to ensure compliance with the law. The Ministry of Education, through the Secretariat of Special

Education, is currently not concerned with punishing; but, get schools to understand their role and the law and act to put all of this into practice.

It draws attention for an authority in education to claim that any teacher, lacking control over the special needs of their students, can teach and still do a good job. Only if this professional is more intellectually disabled than the students he serves, or if he has no idea what the teaching profession is, which requires minimal knowledge about the object in question and its psychology; how they behave, how they respond to the teacher's interests and how they can create a dialogue during classes, since interaction between the parties is essential for the student to achieve dignified, autonomous learning.

LEGISLATION THAT SUPPORTS INCLUSIVE EDUCATION

According to the Federal Constitution, “education, a right for all and a duty of the State and the family, will be promoted and encouraged with the collaboration of society (...)” (BRASIL, 1988, p. 36). In itself, this article would be valid for people with disabilities. Furthermore, the document also reassures that, “(...) specialized educational assistance for people with disabilities, preferably in the regular education network” (Id.; Ibid.). Likewise, Federal Law 7,853 provides support for disabled people and their social integration, defining prejudice as a crime. In this sense, no school or daycare center can refuse, without just cause, access to the institution for a disabled person. The penalty for offenders is one to four years in prison in addition to a fine. Finally, in CNE/CEB resolution no. 2, which establishes national guidelines for Special Education in Basic Education, in article 1 in a single paragraph that:

The school assistance for these students will begin in Early Childhood Education, in daycare centers and preschools, providing them with special education services whenever the need for specialized educational assistance becomes evident through assessment and interaction with the family and community (BRAZIL, 2001, sp).

Therefore, it appears that education is a right for everyone, and based on this principle, educational assistance to people with special needs, in a common school environment or in specialized groups, is ensured by the aforementioned law and even in the Guidelines Law and Bases of National Education.

Chapter V – “Special Education” – of the National Education Guidelines and Bases Law (LDB No. 9,394/96), proposes actions, which have demonstrated the openness of the service

process and guarantee of introducing innovations into it, with the aim of ensure greater possibilities for people with disabilities to interact with society (BRASIL, 1996).

With this new vision, social inclusion begins to mean a process of adaptation of society, by including people with special needs in all social environments, including early childhood education. This makes it possible for, at the same time, these children to prepare to take their place in society, and to play the roles appropriate to each situation.

In order for the child with special needs and the school to feel able to participate in this integration, good preparation is necessary, as, in the current proposal, everyone is expected to have devices that help their school development plan . Therefore, according to the laws, inclusion in regular schools must be a gradual process, which respects the different needs and interests of each child. First of all, it is necessary to check whether she is prepared to attend a common class, in which the differences will be highlighted by comparison with other classmates. To achieve this, it is of fundamental importance that the family provides teachers with the necessary data so that they can better understand the new situation, and can predict the child's type of reaction in the school environment. This data includes medical opinion, results and information from psychologists, among other data.

Mazzotta (1999) states that the integration of children with special needs in the educational process implies reciprocity. And the pedagogical process based on interaction must be gradual and dynamic, adapted to the needs of each individual.

With the guarantee of the right to be enrolled in a regular school, an exchange of experiences, professionals and material is now emerging, bringing the two educational systems closer together: special and regular.

Professionals and specialists play a very important role in this process of effective interaction, which is to demystify the issue of coexistence and education for children with special needs.

The regular school, in turn, also needs to have resources that make the inclusion process viable, for example, contact with teachers who have experienced similar situations; guidance for Special Education teachers, itinerant teachers and resource rooms. Meetings can be held to exchange experiences, discuss different approaches to the content and clarify doubts regarding action and evaluation plans (CORREIA, 1999, p. 143).

In this sense, it can be said that at all school levels (infant, elementary, secondary and higher education), it is necessary to take into account both common and specialized school learning, that there is a subject who needs to develop, learn the content school program and acquire knowledge of the world of oneself (social/school/psychic). What characterizes the

student is their learning capacity, and not the disability they present, as there is a subject with potential, in which one should invest.

In both common and specialized education, the student must be involved in the learning process, because, by actually participating, they will be able to make responsible choices and plan for the future, since the curricular content to be developed by the teacher of common school is based on the National Curricular Parameters (PCN's). The use of varied materials (newspapers, magazines, advertisements, TV news, among others) contributes to motivating students, keeping them up to date with world events, giving them a broad view of events, in this aspect, the role of teacher consists of promoting the understanding of information, so that the proposals of the PCNs, and the curricular content itself, favor integration, as they are based on the interaction of students with each other throughout the activities - in the group, in the class, at school and in the community. Because, it is part of the educational process to learn to respect differences and carry out supportive activities.

Da Ross (1999) is adamant in stating that, whatever the type of education received, special or not, people with disabilities do not just need school, it is essential that they are offered care in the medical aspects related to their disability, as well such as family guidance and emotional support, seeking to facilitate the development of their potential, encouraging them to make choices and take responsibility for them and offering them the same opportunities available to people who do not have disabilities.

However, the fight for social participation is not just a fight for people with disabilities and their families. When talking about integration, or currently insertion, it is essential that society does its part, using all means to meet the difficulties imposed by disability.

Receiving people with disabilities and facilitating their access to all social places, especially at school, from Early Childhood Education onwards, is the legally supported counterpart for their integration and participation in society.

INCLUSIVE INSTITUTION - A SCHOOL FOR ALL

The practice of social inclusion is based on different principles than conventional ones: acceptance of individual differences, valuing each person, coexistence within human diversity, learning through cooperation.

Inclusion, unlike integration, does not require that the burden of participation falls solely on children with disabilities, but rather that it be shared with the society that surrounds them. The interaction is content with the unilateral effort of disabled children to join society.

Inclusion, in turn, requires fundamental changes in the common systems of society, so that all people, disabled or not, are first together, included and then able to rehabilitate themselves, play, study, work, receive medical care, experience, between others. The goal of inclusion is, from the beginning, to not leave anyone out of the school system, which will have to adapt to the particularities of all students.

The Declaration of Salamanca, Spain (1994, World Conference on Special Education, UNESCO), brings in its message that education from a school perspective is a matter of human rights, and individuals with disabilities must be part of schools, which must modify its operation to include all students, based on the fundamental principle that everyone should learn together, regardless of any difficulties or differences they may have.

In an inclusive school, an educational system must be created that considers the needs of all students, and this system is structured according to these needs. Bringing inclusion a change in the educational perspective, where it is not limited to helping only students who have difficulties, but seeks to support everyone: teachers, students, administrative staff, achieving educational success (MANTOAN, 1998, p. 21).

The first step would be the awareness and training of the institution's employees: teachers, attendants, advisors and everyone who works at the institution. Parental awareness is also very important, especially non-disabled parents, thus playing an active role in the inclusion process.

Students with disabilities:

They learn to enjoy diversity; they gain direct experience with the variety of human capabilities. Demonstrate increasing responsibility and better learning through group work, with others, disabled or not; they are better prepared for adult life in a diverse society; they understand that they are different, but not inferior (MILLER, 2002, p. 117).

Students without disabilities:

It has access to a much wider range of social roles; they lose fear and prejudice towards what is different; develop cooperation and tolerance; they acquire a great sense of responsibility and improve school performance; They are better prepared for adult life because they learn from an early age that people, families and social spaces are not homogeneous and that differences are enriching for human beings (MILLER, 2002, p. 117).

Inclusion is a process for which there are no ready-made formulas, it requires everyone to be constantly improving and building. A permanent search for guidance and support from assistance associations and medical and educational authorities.

From a pedagogical point of view, according to Montoan (2007), this construction implies transforming Day Care Centers and Early Childhood Education Centers, with regard to curriculum, assessment and, mainly, attitudes, considering that

The practice of inclusion must be aimed at a totally different relationship between parents and coaches, parents and children, coaches and children, teachers and students, supervisors and employees. A practice that treats the special child as a desiring subject (MANTOAN, 1998, p. 25).

For Emília Ferreiro, Vygotsky (2001) and many others, the process of acquiring knowledge is a construction, and in this construction there are steps to be achieved; Often, what are mistakes now become a way of learning to get things right later. This is a different proposal for dealing with children at any age, whether they have a disability or not.

Canzian (1997) reports some procedures that could be adopted by daycare centers and Early Childhood Education Centers:

- a) Group work and varied activities that may have different levels of understanding and performance
- b) Predominance of experimentation, creation, discovery and co-authorship of knowledge.
- c) Preparation of debates and records, research and exchange of experiences between the teaching staff and the community.
- d) Assessment of the class's development from the point of view of the evolution of skills.

Despite the great advances and the firm action of the MEC in promoting inclusion, we are still far from effectively achieving perfection. The goal is to include all children, that is, to ensure that they all have a quality education from an early age, absolutely all: disabled, poor, black, marginalized, no one should be excluded. It is a process, a challenge and at the same time an emotional exchange. However, it is recommended that disabled people with severe impairment be referred for specialized assessments at competent entities such as APAE, where they will receive psychological and therapeutic support in extracurricular care.

LDB nº 9,394/96 (Law of Guidelines and Bases of National Education) recognizes the importance of training regular education teachers to receive students with special needs in their classrooms, as a prerequisite for inclusion by establishing, in its article 59, what:

Education systems will ensure that students with special needs are:” “III – Teachers with appropriate specialization at secondary or higher level, for specialized assistance, as well as regular education teachers trained to integrate these students into regular classes... (BRAZIL, LDB n° 9,394/96, op. cit.).

This article makes it clear that quality teaching for children with special needs, from the perspective of inclusive education, involves at least two types of professional teaching training: *generalist teachers* in regular education, with a minimum of knowledge and practice regarding diverse students; and teachers *specializing* in different special educational needs.

The teacher, acting in accordance with the training received, tends to privilege certain contents to the detriment of others. In this way, knowledge can present itself in a repetitive circle that is disconnected from the student's reality, which causes the subject to continually maintain an alienated practice. This is what has happened to most teachers at daycare centers and early childhood education centers.

However, it is important to highlight that they act this way because they did not receive sufficient guidance in their training and training courses to enable them to structure their pedagogical practice to meet the different ways of learning of their young students.

Thus, the transformation of the school, into a space without barriers, of quality and receptive to all students, necessarily involves the transformation of the teacher. It is not just about teaching these professionals specific pedagogical techniques and resources, not limited to academic knowledge of the needs of their students. It is necessary to rethink your pedagogical and personal stance, given the changes suffered by society, seeking to guarantee the learning of all students, whether in special or regular education.

Inclusive education, despite still encountering serious resistance (legitimate or prejudiced) from many educators, undoubtedly constitutes a proposal that seeks to rescue fundamental social values, consistent with equal rights and opportunities for all. However, for the inclusion of students with special needs in the regular Early Childhood Education system to be effective, enabling the recovery of citizenship and the expansion of existing expectations, it is not enough to enact laws that determine the creation of basic teacher training courses, nor mandatory enrollment in public schools. These are undoubtedly essential measures, but not sufficient.

Public policies for inclusion should be implemented in the form of training and continuous monitoring programs, which guide teaching work with a view to reducing school exclusion, which would benefit not only students with special needs, but in general , Early Childhood Education as a whole.

According to Ferreira (1998), participating in an inclusive process means being predisposed, above all, to consider and respect individual differences, creating the possibility of learning about oneself and others, in situations of diversity of ideas, feelings and actions. With this assumption, it is suggested that the inclusion of children with disabilities is a teaching-learning process where the teacher and the student learn and teach.

From this perspective, the teacher needs to leave the place of object, who appropriates the practice, and feel like the subject of their actions, grounding themselves theoretically, supporting the construction of knowledge, whether on a personal or collective level.

For inclusion to be true, the school needs to assume its share of responsibility, understanding that the difficulties of many students are not just theirs, but result, in large part, from the way teaching is delivered, learning is conceived and evaluated. . Embedded in this issue, it is considered that the construction of a pedagogical project necessarily involves ideas coming from the school community, seeking a balance between expectations and possibilities for the student's development.

According to Carvalho (1997, p. 79), the professional's performance in the inclusion situation reflects: “An attitude of non-rejection, with interactive exchanges between colleagues, appreciation of self-image and self-esteem. An attitude of non-segregation, where the difficulty of promoting interactive exchanges predominates”.

From this perspective, it is observed that professionals who do not promote inclusion have an attitude of disaggregation, understanding that due to learning difficulties or differences, this student should be in segregated contexts; or consider themselves lacking the knowledge to work with diversity, not knowing how and what to do.

Different professional profiles highlight different characteristics in relation to coexistence with difference, with diversity. The non-inclusive professional would have to give new meaning to pedagogical practice and the conception he attributes to diversity. Carvalho (1999) states that this change in attitude regarding difference involves the entire school community.

According to Correia (1999), disability is not exactly the problem. The inclusive professional accepts the idea of the *kaleidoscope* , that is, everyone is important and significant: the greater the diversity, the more complex and richer the learning will be. For him, the student is a being in the process of growth and development, who experiences the teaching-learning process in different ways, whether due to their individual differences or their interests and motivations.

According to Canzian (1997), this professional, in general, is able to identify himself as a learning professional and not as a teaching professional, seeking to transform his classes into pleasurable spaces, where both he and his students are complicit in an adventure that is learning to learn and learning to think, because,

It seeks to use more participatory strategies, including group work, which favors the exchange of experiences and cooperation. The teacher who adopts the inclusive education proposal must consider the student as an important resource in the classroom and takes advantage of the thematic proposals that emerge in groups, valuing individual differences and the potential of students (DEMO *apud* CARVALHO, 1997, p. 121).

Everything exposed by the aforementioned author refers to didactic actions that can be carried out in classrooms, with a view to creating an inclusive environment and symbolic exchanges of experiences. Respect for others should never be imposed; this must be based on an individual achievement and be recognized collectively.

CONCLUSION

Inclusion is an innovation, the meaning of which has been very distorted and a movement highly controversial among the most different educational and social segments. However, including students with deficits of all kinds, permanent or temporary, more serious or less severe, in regular education is nothing more than guaranteeing everyone's right to education - as stated in the 1988 Constitution.

Innovating does not necessarily mean the unusual. Great innovations are often in the implementation of the obvious, the simple, what is possible to do, but which needs to be unveiled, so that it can be understood by everyone and accepted without other resistance, other than those that give brightness and vigor to the debate of news. Inclusion, as a consequence of quality teaching for all students, provokes and demands new positions from Brazilian schools and is one more reason for teaching to be modernized and for teachers to improve their practices. It is an innovation that implies an effort to update and restructure the current conditions of the majority of our basic schools.

The reason that supports the fight for inclusion as a new perspective for people with disabilities is, without a doubt, the quality of teaching in public and private schools, so that they are able to respond to the needs of each of their students, according to their specificities, without falling into the web of special education and its forms of exclusion.

The success of including students with disabilities in regular schools arises, therefore, from the possibilities of achieving significant progress for these students in schooling, through the adaptation of pedagogical practices to the diversity of learners. And this success can only be achieved when regular schools accept that the difficulties of some students are not just theirs, but largely result from the way teaching is delivered, learning is conceived and evaluated. Because, not only disabled people are excluded, but also those who are poor, those who don't go to classes because they work, those who belong to discriminated groups, those who have given up studying after so many repetitions. In this sense, it is essential that the roles played by directors and coordinators are reviewed, in the sense that they go beyond the controlling, supervisory and bureaucratic content of their functions to support work and guide the teacher and the entire school community.

The inclusive movement in schools, even though it is still highly contested, due to the threatening nature of any and all changes, especially in the educational environment, is irreversible and convinces everyone by its logic, by the ethics of its social positioning.

Inclusion reveals this distance that needs to be filled with immediate actions. Therefore, the future of the inclusive school is, in our view, depending on a rapid expansion of projects truly imbued with the commitment to transform the school, to adapt to the new times. If today they are still local experiences, those that are demonstrating the viability of inclusion, in Brazilian schools and education networks, these experiences have the strength of the obvious and the clarity of simplicity and these virtues alone are enough to foresee the growth of this new paradigm in the educational system. The implementation of quality schools, which are egalitarian, fair and welcoming to everyone, is a possible dream. The apparent fragility of small initiatives, that is, those local experiences that have been sufficient to face the power of the old and rusty educational machine, with security and tranquility. These initiatives have shown the viability of school inclusion in Brazilian schools.

The perspectives of inclusive education are, therefore, encouraging and encouraging for education in Brazil. The school belongs to the people, to all children, their families, the communities in which they are inserted. Considering this fact, the following is recorded as a suggestion for resuming this topic in a next specialization course: comparing the development achieved by children and adolescents who have been enrolled in special schools and regular schools, with the aim of seeing what each system can do for the benefit of those with special needs.

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